

TRADITIONAL JUDICIAL SYSTEM IN PRE-COLONIAL EDDA, EBONYI STATE (1800-1900)

¹Nnenna Onyeaka Oji and ²Dr. Paul U. Omeje

¹Department of social sciences, Akanu ibiam federal polytechnic, Afikpo, Ebonyi State, Nigeria.

²Department of History/International Relations, Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki, Ebonyi State, Nigeria.

ORCID: 0009-0008-6478-5712

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Abstract: Traditional institutions in Igboland are as old as the people and have played numerous roles in the development of the people. They are arranged and have structured governance, order and conflict resolution. In pre-colonial Edda, these institutions constitute an effective indigenous judicial system that regulated social relations and maintained communal stability. This study examines the structure, functions and significance of the traditional judicial system in pre-colonial Edda, with particular emphasis on institutions such as the age grade, council of elders, lineage heads, and other customary authority. Drawing from both primary and secondary source, the paper argues that the institutions played a central and often decisive role in the administration of justice, enforcement of decisions, and maintenance of peace at the grassroots levels. The study further shows that the judicial processes in Edda were participatory, restorative and guided by established customs and moral codes that ensured social cohesion rather than just punitive isolation. However, the advent of colonial rule and foreign religion introduced new legal frameworks that gradually destabilized and in some of these indigenous institutions. Despite these transformations, elements of the traditional judicial system have persisted and continued to influence contemporary dispute resolution in Edda. The paper concludes that the pre-colonial judicial system in Edda was not only functional but highly adaptive and its principles remain relevant to understanding local governance and justice in present day Igboland.

Keyword: Traditional institution, Edda, indigenous justice, conflict resolution, Age Grade, Peace, Security.

Introduction

Pre-colonial Igbo societies practiced traditional judicial systems which served as the bedrock of social order and conflict resolution within various communities. Anchored on reliance on customary laws, the involvement of community elders, and a focus on restorative justice, these systems were fixed in the cultural and social life of Igbo societies. There were several customary laws that regulated different aspects of life such as marriage, inheritance, funerals and land ownership. These laws were enforced by traditional leaders, who were responsible for maintaining order and ensuring justice was served.

The judicial system in Pre-colonial Edda from 1800 to 1900 was a multifaceted and intricate network of legal procedures and institutions. It was heavily influenced by the people cultural and societal norms, who had a strong believe in justice and fairness. At the centre of the Edda judicial system was the council of elders responsible for settling disputes, enforcing laws, and maintaining order within the community. They were highly respected and their decisions were final. They presided over various courts, each with their own specific

jurisdiction. One unique feature of the Edda judicial system was the use of divination to determine guilt or innocence. This involved rituals and ceremonies that were believed to reveal the truth in a dispute. While this may seem unconventional to modern standards, it was an essential part of the Edda people's belief system and was widely accepted in the clan. No doubt, colonialism and the introduction of foreign religion have impacted on the judicial system in Edda, which led to certain changes and sometimes relegation of the institution. Despite the impact of colonial rule and the introduction of formal legal systems, traditional judicial systems have persisted and continued to play a crucial role in many African communities (Boege, 2006).

The diversity of ethnic groups in Nigeria has given rise to a rich range of traditional judicial practices. Each ethnic group, with its unique customs and traditions, has developed distinct judicial systems that address the specific needs of their communities (Paden, 1973). For instance, among the Yoruba in the southwest, the judicial system revolves around the *Oba* (king) and his council of chiefs (*Ijoye*), who mediate disputes and ensure social harmony through customary laws and public hearings (Last, 1967). While in northern Nigeria, the judicial system of the Hausa-Fulani centres on the Islamic law (*Sharia*), with the Emir and his council adjudicating matters based on a blend of customary and religious law (Afigbo, 1981). The Igbo people of South Eastern Nigeria have a decentralized traditional judicial system that follows the way they are organized in autonomous communities which is usually overseen by a council of elders (*Ndeichie*) (Nwolise, 2001). These elders, respected for their wisdom and experience, are pivotal in interpreting and enforcing customary laws. The Igbo judicial process is participatory, it involves various age-grades (*uke/ogbo*) and sometimes secret societies such as the *Ekpe* and *Egbela*, which plays significant roles in maintaining social order and enforcing judicial decisions (Alubo, 2011).

The Igbo traditional judicial system is notable for its emphasis on restorative justice. Unlike Western legal systems that prioritize punishment, the Igbo traditional approach focuses on reconciliation and restoring community harmony. Disputes were resolved through mediation and arbitration, with decisions usually involving compensation, fines, and reconciliatory ceremonies intended to mend relationships and reintegrate offenders into the community (Arunsi, 1994). Public participation in judicial proceedings ensured transparency and reinforces communal values, which makes the process an integral part of Igbo social life.

Despite the pressures of modernization and the influence of formal legal systems introduced during the colonial rule, traditional judicial systems in Edda have shown remarkable resilience. They continue to coexist with formal courts, particularly in rural areas where access to state legal institutions may be limited. This coexistence allows for a hybrid legal structure that leverages the strengths of both traditional and formal systems, providing accessible and culturally relevant justice to communities (Basden, 1992). It is against this background that this paper seeks to identify the roles of traditional judicial organs in pre-colonial Edda, its role in maintaining a sane and secured community, as well as general administration of a traditional society.

The study adopted Restorative Justice Theory which emerged as a modern concept in the 1970s through the work of different scholars. Albert Eglash however, coined the term Restorative Justice, although Howard Zehr is known as the father of modern restorative justice who laid its foundation (Englash, 1977). The theory is ingrained in community based conflict resolution and is closely related to the traditional judicial system of Edda. It lays emphasises on repairing harm caused by wrong doing and reconciliation between offender, the victim and the community. Edda judicial system relied much on mediation, compensation, reintegration and

restoration of relationships and maintaining harmony which perfectly aligns the topic with restorative justice principles. Restorative justice provides a suitable framework for analysing the traditional judicial system in pre-colonial Edda as they both practices restoring relationships and maintaining communal peace and tranquillity. Understanding Edda's traditional judicial system through the lens of restorative justice, will gain insight into the methods of conflict resolution.

Literature review

Secondary materials in favour of the topic are scarce. As a result of the scarcity of literature on traditional judicial system in pre-colonial Edda, a few works on Edda were reviewed in the course of this research. In an effort to review some historical works by scholars, there is need to summarise, paraphrase and possibly quote some of this works that are related to the present study.

S.I Arunsi & J. U Ugoji's book titled, '*Edda Heritage*' took a historical survey of Edda clan. They penned down a detailed history of Edda from her origin to her migration and settlement. This book is one of the most popular Literature on Edda by Edda scholars. Ugoji & Arunsi gave a detailed analysis on the people and culture of Edda, from the climate to marriage, age grade system and women's involvement. Edda Heritage discusses the judicial system of Edda people, but as a part of their socio-political structures (Arunsi, 1994).

Uka Ugwuocha Uka's '*Edda land matters: customs, inheritance and traditional legal system*' the book said a lot about the intricate land tenure system in Edda, inheritance customs, and traditional legal framework of the people (Ugwuocha, 2024). He paid close attention on how land is owned, transferred and inherited in Edda. He highlights the role of family and communal relationship as long as land is concerned in Edda, and gave detailed legal practices which will be valuable for mostly legal practitioners and scholars interested in customary law and indigenous land tenure system. However, the literature was lacking in the area of the topic of discourse.

Udu Ukpai Okoro's '*Towards the rebirth of Edda*' wrote basically on the developmental challenges which affect Edda. Udu proffered his thought on the struggling youths of Edda and maintained that their thought habit have been a limitation towards a new and better developed Edda. He analysed the static development of Edda from the pre- colonial period. In his words 'apart from her poor physical development, Edda's backwardness is even more graphically buttressed by her lack of developed human resources' (Okoro, 1999). He narrates Edda's backwardness in business, political, social and academic pursuits. This book is very useful to a great extent as it reveals the developmental process of Edda, but it fell short of expectations as nothing was said pertaining to our topic of discussion.

In addition, Uka U. Uka, '*Edda: a people and her culture*' (Uka, 2009) also took the toll of other Edda scholars. He laid emphasis on the economic and socio-political development of Edda. Uka dedicated the whole of the book's second chapter to economic development of the region. He dedicated a chapter to the economic development of Edda, and the traditional judicial system of pre-colonial Edda. But failed to mention the inability of the poor to get justice because of bribery, corruption and other vices.

Arua Oko, Ikenna U. Unya & Iduma Igariway's book '*The Bond a study of intergroup relations between Afikpo and Edda*' (Arua etal, 2022) which happens to be the first scholarly survey on Afikpo and Edda as an entity, examined the historic origin, cultural heritage and economic development of Edda and Afikpo clans. Like other scholars, they wrote extensively on the history of Edda and that of Afikpo, but went further to analyse the influence of western education and Christian missionary activities in the areas. They gave detailed analysis of

the traditional economy of Edda and Afikpo which stands them out from other indigenous scholars. According to the scholars, 'the interesting thing about traditional markets in Edda and Afikpo is that they are largely controlled by women'. They were not able to delve into the traditional judicial system of pre-colonial Edda.

A brief on Edda

Edda, traditionally known as Edda Egbebu is currently one of the local government Areas in Ebonyi State, Nigeria. It lies within the south-eastern region of Nigeria, characterized by a mix of savannah and forest landscapes. The area is known for its undulating terrain, spread with hills and valleys, which has influenced the settlement patterns and socio-political organization of its inhabitants. Edda people are part of the larger Igbo ethnic group, known for their rich cultural heritage and complex social structures. In the pre-colonial era, Edda was organized into clans and villages, each governed by a council of elder and led by a chief or king (*Ezeogo*). The social hierarchy and community cohesion were maintained through kinship ties, age-grade systems, and secret societies, which played crucial roles in governance and social control.

Edda is located in the Southern Senatorial zone of Ebonyi state of Nigeria and is made up of seventy two villages with hamlets (*ezi*) constituting secondary units for each of them. These seventy two villages were divided into ten autonomous communities that include Amangwu, Amato, Ebunwana, Ekoli, Etiti, Idima, Nguzu, Umunna, Oso and Owutu autonomous communities. Prior to the institution of autonomous communities in Igboland, Edda was administratively structured into Ndeelu (upper Edda) and Ndagbo (lower Edda). Edda immediate neighbours are: Ehugbo, Amasiri and Akaeze in the north. On the South Edda is bounded by Ohafia, on the East by Erie and Unwana and on the West by Nkporo and Okagwe Ohafia (Arunsi, 1994). Aside these close neighbouring communities, Abam, Abiriba, Arochukwu among others constitute distant neighbours of Edda with whom they share cultural similarities and had formed alliance to prosecute their pre-colonial wars. Edda has similar climate with her neighbours and enjoys cordial relationship with her them through inter-marriage, trade and commerce. Edda people are bound by ties of blood (*nwanne*) based on double descent arrangement of matrilineal (*ikwunne*) and patrilineal (*Ikwunna*) families. Ikwunne is one common bond that unites the people. Edda is also classified as Cross River Igbo and shares the same language with other Igbo communities albeit, with dialectical variation which is common in Igboland.

On the aspect of origin and migration of the Edda people, two traditions of origin exist. First is the oriental or hermitic hypothesis which traces the Edda origin to the Middle East. This account labels Egypt as the take off point in the Edda migration. Proponents to this hypothesis on the Edda story of origin are G.T. Basden, who has based his argument on the semblance in the Igbo and Jewish cultures (Basden, 1992) The second tradition of origin links Edda origin to the neighbouring Cross River region. A.E. Afigbo, has opposed the oriental hypothesis on the Edda Origin as not convincing. Evidences such as similarities in language and pigmentation between the Edda people and the Middle East people in this regard appear to be completely lacking (Afigbo, 1983). More so, artefacts such as pieces of earthen pots and implement carved with stones and radio carbon dated as back as 2,935BC to 670BC and 15 AD, reveals more that human settlement took place in the area under review prior to the time of the alleged migration from the Middle East as peddled in the oriental or hermitic hypothesis. Therefore, the origin and migration of the Edda people is better understood when traced internally within Igboland.

Structures of Traditional Judicial System in Pre-Colonial Edda

The traditional judicial system in Edda holds significant cultural importance, showing the traditional African justice mechanisms that prioritize community participation, reconciliation, and harmony (John .I, 2025 oral interview). This system, ingrained in the community, represents principles of accessibility, informality, and collective negotiation, aligning with the needs of marginalized and disadvantaged populations (Nnachi, 2018). The traditional significance of the judicial system in Edda not only serves as a means of conflict resolution but also helped in preserving cultural heritage and promoting social cohesion within the clan.

Pre-colonial Edda clan was made up of six communities which existed independently and carried out their judicial matters independently, known today as common laws. This includes customs and traditions, norms and values of the people. Males and females in Edda clan knew their roles from home. Adolescence separates the male and female roles from home, thereby allowing the father and mother role to play in. The child is naturally nurtured from home, and understands how to do things systematically at home then to the community. The constitutions were unwritten as well as the acts of parliaments. Edda Judicial proceedings were held in various stages starting from the family to the compound, the village and finally a public hearing at the clan level which usually takes place at Osisoma and Atamata. Osisoma Edda is the judicial headquarters of Edda and holds a significant place in the peace and unity of the entire clan. Overtime, it has played great role in ensuring justice, retribution and promoting transparency.

The first institution of government in pre-colonial Edda begins with *nde eze isi ogo* (village chiefs) and the totality of the village chiefs becomes *nzuko nde eze*. Things were separated according to hierarchy; those in charge of the *ofor*, and those entitled to the head or jaws of cows when slaughtered. There were leaders among the village heads who performs the judicial function on consensus basis (Azuenya, 2025 oral interview). The next in line are *nde isina* (the nobles), these people must have concluded different levels of *egbela* cult initiation to become *nde Nze*. The older ones are known as *akasi nde isina* (younger chiefs) while the younger ones are called *okpiti nde isina* (older chiefs) who also become chiefs by tradition and can be coopted into *nde eze* (traditional rulers) to make laws and adjudication. It is this chiefs and *nde isina* (council of elders) that constitutes the parliament, when they work together and constitutes the judiciary.

When matters were reported for arbitration, both the accused and the accusers were invited, the *Eze* (king) brings out a coin and kisses it then drop it and tell the two parties to testify truthfully because they are under an oath. After questions and cross examinations by *nde ishini* (elders), the cabinet meets (*igba izu*) and weigh the case with judgment being given accurately. If any party felt dissatisfied, it can appeal to the higher body which consist of *nde Eze* (kings). Litigations were done at the native court. However, when there were issue that effects the entire Edda clan, the six paramount rulers and *nde isina* heads to *Atamata* to deliberate and decide on matters and head to *Osisoma* for execution (Obo, 2025 oral interview). Executions are given based on what was arrived at. There are no deliberations at *Osisoma* but only executions, while announcements were made at *Achi nze Ikpe*. Once the court converges at *Osisoma*, there is no going back on the execution. If it is a case of banishment, it takes effect from there. Judicial and political organizations were centred at *Atamata* in Nguzu, *Osisoma* in Letu and *Achi nze ikpe* in Owutu. Deliberations were basically done at *Atamata* and *Achi nze Ikpe* on major binding decisions on crucial issues such as declaration of wars and legislations on matters affecting

the entire clan, while public hearing and executions on matters were done at Osisioma. In the light of such occasion, the traditional rulers (*Eze ogos*) from all the villages of Edda and some elders would converge at the historical spot (Atamata). Decisions reached at Osisioma were irrevocable and binding on both individuals and communities in Edda. Decisions taken at Osisioma could include but not limited to banishment and burying individuals alive depending on their offences (Ewa, 2025 oral interview).

In Edda tradition, convergence at Osisioma was done on specific periods of the year and must be for crucial matters. Osisioma was patterned more like a general assembly. Attendance was also mandatory for *ezeogo* and *nde isina* as leaders of representatives of communities. Once a matter is taken to Osisioma, it is usually irreversible, deliberations at both Osisioma and Atamata were strictly for Ezeogos and nde Ishina, and women were not allowed to converge (Ewa, 2025). The traditional judicial system of pre-colonial Edda provides valuable insights into the broader Igbo society and the ways in which indigenous African communities maintained order and resolved conflicts before the advent of colonial rule.

The judicial system of pre-colonial Edda was decentralized but highly structured. Each village was semi-autonomous, with its council of elders (*Nde isina*) and various age-grades (*uke*) managing local affairs. The system was an integral part of the political structure, with the council of elders serving as the primary adjudicators of disputes and enforcers of customary laws. The *Eze* (king), while often seen as the highest authority, typically acted in consultation with the elders, ensuring that decisions were communal and reflective of societal norms. Edda's significance during the pre-colonial era stemmed from its well-organized social and political systems, which facilitated peace and stability within the community. The intricate network of laws and customs ensured that justice was administered though not fairly in all the cases, maintaining social harmony. Additionally, the cultural practices and institutions of Edda have had a lasting impact, with many traditional customs and governance structures persisting into the modern era

Features of the Traditional Judicial Systems

Traditional Edda justice mechanisms highlights community leaders' central role, active community participation, reconciliation, and harmony These systems, like traditional peace building, offer a community-friendly option for resolving conflicts, especially in land disputes, promoting restorative justice, inclusiveness, and peace. The pre-colonial judicial system in Edda were fused or combined together into; the legislative, judicial and executive system. There were systems of leadership in the pre-colonial Edda. Edda had two systems of leadership; the shrine and the spiritual aspect which the Eze Edda chaired the meetings. Pre-colonial Edda was more of a confederate arrangement, there were members of the confederate council which consisted of leaders of various villages (*Ogo*) and *nde isina* (Okoro, 1999).

The native authority in Edda court which consist of the Ezeogo of various clans and council of elders (*nde isina*). It is worthy of note that, traditional institutions in Edda historically served as mediators, conflict resolvers, and administrators. They played crucial role in maintaining peace, resolving disputes, and preserving cultural heritage within the society. Traditional rulers in Edda were respected for preserving culture and resolving conflicts. The traditional judicial system in Edda was organized hierarchically, involving different levels of authority:

a. Traditional rulers (*Nde Ezeogo*): The titular head of a village or town in Edda is known as the *Ezeogo*, a title which corresponds with *Igwe* in some Igbo traditional setting. The *Ezeogo* otherwise known as paramount

rulers in colonial era are leaders of community who have been distinguished in character and integrity in charge of an autonomous community. They are conferred through rigorous selection process that involves community nomination, king's makers' deliberation, spiritual cleansing and ceremonies. The *Ezeogo* had the highest judicial authority, overseeing major dispute and making final decisions on critical issues, ensuring fairness and adherence to tradition. He was to guide the community, resolving conflicts and disputes, enforcing law and order, providing physical and spiritual leadership and preserving the culture and tradition of the people. He was never an autocrat because his decisions were often made in consultation with the council of elders, who were leaders from various lineages.

b. Council of Elders (Nde Ishina): Disputes are literally resolved by the council of elders as they act as mediators, arbiters and custodians of the law. They are important members of the judicial system. Cases are reported to them first at the ezi level, cases difficult for them to settle were then taken to *nde Eze*. The elders were responsible for interpreting and enforcing customary laws. They were deeply respected and held significant influence. *Nde ishina* is by induction in Edda, they are separated from an age grade (*uke ji ogo*), and inducted into the council of elders. They work with the *Ezeogo* and *Nze* in decision making, consultations and deliberations. *Nde ishina* in Edda were in different categories and levels – *Nde isina oma Ogo*, *nde isina Ifu ogo* and *nde isina ntu* (who are the oldest amongst them). Their judgements were based on community customs and tradition, and their goal as to maintain harmony rather than punish.

c. Age-Grade Groups (Uke): The traditional judicial and socio-political picture of Edda will not be complete without the age grade, which has played the most significant role in the judicial system of Edda (Arua et al, 2022). Age grade known as 'Uke' in Edda, is a group of people born within a given age bracket who come together to form an organized working system or ally. 'Uke' is a common place in Edda that provides a strong social structure. People within the age difference of three to seven years form an age grade. Males and females belong to the same age grade, and work together on matters of mutual interest. Age grade system has lasted in Edda and had changing roles depending on the tempo and trend of the wider community. They could move from being sole source of warriors used to cause terror and sorrow to other Igbo communities to an effective instrument for initiating and executing important social and judicial issues in various Edda towns.

In pre-colonial Edda, age grade served as a tool for governance, social mobilization, development, security and social control and has remained one of the most power forces for the provision of political leadership of the people. The system also helped to create a sense of oneness, discipline and cohesion among the people. It constitutes a system through which the various villages co-operate for war, peace, work, governance and entertainment.

These groups helped mediate and enforce decisions. Time and events have caused trends in the functions of age grades in Edda. For instance, in the pre-colonial period, '*Ukejiogo*' (strength of the community) have been the warriors that protected the community from external invasion. Going further, at the inception of colonial rule, it was apparent that war had become one of the means adopted by the earliest inhabitants... to solve the problem arising from their internal readjustment. This is the administrative age grade. Oral tradition illustrates the realization of the importance of the army in protecting the community from external aggression and in prosecuting their own wars (Uka, 2025 oral interview).

Just like every other Igbo community, there was no standing army as troops were raised when the need arose. In Edda, age grades constituted military structure from where the soldiers were drawn (Arunsi, 1994). No doubt, every able bodied young man participated in the wars; age grades remained the only platform for their categorization, mobilization and control. They also conducted peace talks amongst Edda communities and between Edda and their neighbours to bring their feuds to peaceful resolutions (Aja, 2015). In fact, there is no aspect of Edda life that can be mentioned without a link to the age grade system. Age grades were often used in manipulating justice in traditional judicial system of pre-colonial Edda. They were used by the rich to avert justice from the poor. For instance, the defendant could be accused of one social vices or another by the age grade leaders who must have been bribed by the defendant.

Edda Legal Codes and Practices

Most of the legal codes and practices in Edda judicial system are based on customary laws and strongly connected to the *Egbela* religious system. These legal codes were usually, symbols of authority or orally transmitted but understood within the community. Some of the customary Laws were derived from traditions and societal values, covering various aspects of life (Isichei, 1977).

The *Omu* (palm fronds)

Omu is an important and highest legal code in Edda. It is a symbol of authority on its own, there were no decisions taken in Pre-colonial Edda without *itu omu* (putting a barricade with the palm frond). It plays dual role; peace identification mark and message. Apart from using them for masquerades, it is very symbolic. For instance, *omu* in Edda is used to settle disputes, if there is a land in dispute, the *ezeogo* and his chiefs in council may give an order for palm fronds to be placed on the entrance of the land and the *Uke ji ogos* (age grade) moves into action. As this point, none of the parties is allowed to enter the disputed land. *Omu* was used as an injunction, once it is placed on the parcel of land, it restricts trespass in the land until the case is settled. There is no revocation when *omu* is placed in a particular place. When *omu* is placed (*itu omu*) anywhere in Edda, everyone is bound to obey it (Obo, 2025). The *Ezeogo* may tie the *omu* to posts in *ogo*, signifying that there is communal work to be done. After important decisions and deliberations that affects Edda clan, decisions are taken at *Atamata*, all the *Ezeogo* would meet at *Osisioma* and are given *oma* to take back home to the people. The significance of *omu* is well known in Edda

***Ekwuru Ekwu*:**

Nde Ekwuru Ekwu are the female leaders of the community, and comprises of women in their 70s and above who have been assessed and known to be upright and truthful. They are custodians of the law and order as long as the female aspect of Edda is concerned. They check immorality and ensure not only the sanity of womanhood but also that of the entire society. Incest have been controlled and curtailed by these set of women. They are dreaded just like the *Egbele* cult. This is because whatever they pronounce on a victim comes to pass. Once there is an abominable act, especially involving a woman or women, they summon the offender or offenders and adjudicate (Nkama, 2025 oral interview). These women meet usually on market days at a sacred and specified location known as '*Ogba afia*' adorned with red beatification chalk (*ufie*). None members are not allowed into their midst. If for any reason one walks into their midst knowingly or unknowingly, you must appease them. Whatever judgment they give brings an end to any form of dispute between women and can never be altered (Ekuma, 2025 oral interview). Most importantly, whatever they asked offenders to pay, they

comply without hesitation. Peradventure the offender refuses to comply, they can decide to go naked and pronounce curses on the offender. It made women conscious of their behaviours and utterances.

Conflict Resolution Mechanisms in Edda

The judicial system employed various methods for resolving disputes; disputes were first deliberated at the *Ikwu* level, then to the *Ezi* and the *ogo*.

a. Arbitration: The council of elders arbitrated more serious disputes, and made binding decisions.

b. Mediation: Elders helped disputing parties reach a mutually agreeable solution.

c. Punishments: Punishments were given based on the magnitude of the offence committed by an individual. The punishments for crimes ranged from death for murder to sale of the offender for theft and compensation for adultery and deformation.

However, corruption and conspiracy were potential threats to the integrity of justice delivery. Corrupt practices existed in pre-colonial judicial system of Edda even though most scholars were unable to document them. Traditional rulers were not entirely free from corrupt practices. In Edda, influential individuals could manipulate outcomes in their favour leading to biased judgments, favouritism and injustice to the ordinary man. This act in most cases undermined the trust of most individuals especially the poor in the judicial process. There were also cases of bribery of the council of elders, and even the custodian of the oracles. These actions could lead to suppression of justice which of course erodes the foundations of communal values. It is worthy of note that majority of corrupt practices of pre-colonial judicial system in Edda are not documented, but understanding in broader terms the traditional Igbo societies provides insight into the challenges they faced in maintaining judicial integrity.

Roles and Functions of the traditional judiciary

The traditional judicial system has played a vital role in maintaining social harmony, resolving disputes, and promoting justice in Edda communities for centuries. Traditional courts provided unique and effective framework for addressing conflicts and promoting social cohesion, cultural heritage and customary practices. These courts served as cornerstone for social order, community governance, providing a platform for dispute resolution, reconciliation, cultural preservation, promotion of traditional values and communal bonds.

The pre-colonial judicial system in Edda played a vital role in maintaining social order, resolving dispute and upholding cultural value.

a. Case Initiation: the aggrieved party reported the dispute to the family head with the details of the disputes, parties involved and the desired mode of resolution. Disputes brought before the council by community members goes through thorough investigations by the council of elders through investigation, consulting with witnesses and deliberation on the situation.

b. Investigation: Council investigated the matter, gathering evidence and testimonies. There were no technicalities; investigations were based on the truth. Were it became difficult to establish the truth, oracles were consulted and divination made. Investigations took the form of gathering information, to consulting the witnesses, and examining the available evidence. In some cases oaths were taken to ascertain the truth. Because truth and fairness was the order of the pre-colonial Edda, there were little fears of impartiality. Bribes were given and received during investigations to cover the truth in favour of the highest bidder.

c. Deliberation: *Nde eze* and council of elders convenes to deliberate, review evidence before them and debate based on evidence. Deliberations were based on collective responsibilities, mutual understanding and respect and maintenance of social harmony. They are bound by an oath to manage conflict of interest and to ensure justice and fairness. In Edda, deliberations were made at *Atamata* in Nguzu Edda, while judgements were passed in Osisioma at Letu depending on the magnitude, while the final announcements were made at Achinzeikpe in Owutu.

d. Judgment: Judgment was based on determination of guilt or innocence. Decisions were made and communicated publicly if necessary, while punishments or restitutions were recommended by the council. Some of the judgments come with either compensations, punishments, reconciliations, ritual cleansing or community service.

e. Enforcement: Enforcement of decisions were dependent on the Age-grade groups (*uke ji ogo*). They were always actively working closely with the Ezeogo. The parties involved in the case were expected to comply with the judgment and the enforcement.

f. Punishment: The judicial system focuses on restorative justice, where offenders are required to compensate victims or perform acts of restitution. Punishments are designed to restore balance rather than inflict harm. But the pre-colonial judicial system was more or less in favour of the rich and influential in the community. Justices was denied the poor in most cases, as the rich tend to influence the decision of the court. Capital punishment was meted to the poor if found guilty, while the rich bribed their way out.

Restoration and Reconciliation processes in Edda judicial system

Disputes in Edda were resolved in gatherings of elders, age grade representatives and a number of selected individuals. This forum encouraged open dialogue, allowing all parties to express their grievances, thereafter seeking for acceptable solutions. The main aim of these gatherings was to mend strained relationships between individuals and families/clans and encouraging social and communal cohesion. Both parties were encouraged to forgive and mend their relationships and ofcourse re-establish trust amongst them.

Justice processes were often done in public courts (*Atamata*, *Osisioma*, *Achi nze ikpe*), allowing some members of the community to observe and contribute. Compensations were often considered over punishments depending on the gravity of the offence. In some cases, spiritual cleansing was expedient to deter deceit. The aggrieved parties were compensated with goods as reparative dispute settlement items. By so doing, the offender remained a functional member of the community even while addressing the harm he/she caused. Rituals often signify the end of a conflict and beginning of a renewed relationship. By focusing on restorative justice, the judicial system in pre-colonial Edda promoted long term peace and stability, were individual wellbeing was tied closely to that of the collective members of the society.

The impact of colonialism on Traditional Judicial Systems

In Nigeria, efforts are being made to enhance the independence of the judiciary through legal, institutional, and textual frameworks, aligning with international standards. Additionally, the digitalization of court proceedings in Nigeria presents both prospects for effective justice administration and challenges related to legal and socio-economic factors, necessitating practical recommendations for stakeholders in the legal sector (Ottenberg, 1959). Incorporating indigenous African governance systems into modern government structures is also suggested to improve governance efficiency and development in post-colonial Africa (Isichei, (1976).

Traditional judicial systems in Africa, and specifically in Igbo land, offer a profound understanding of how indigenous societies manage conflict and maintain social order. The Igbo traditional judicial system exemplifies the rich cultural heritage and communal values that control these practices, highlighting the importance of restorative justice and community involvement in the judicial process. Colonialism brought about a shift in the judicial system of Edda. When the British invaded Nigeria, they wanted to impose their own system on the people. In the case of Edda, it was not very easy to impose the warrant chief system. There were certain areas of the pre-colonial judicial system were adopted while some were killed out rightly.

The pre-colonial judicial Edda was outstanding. The old judicial system and its organisation was associated with truth and uprightness. Colonialism brought in courts which undermines the traditional judicial system of the pre-colonial Edda clan. Its panel and judges were appointed by government, and the traditional council lost most of their power and some of their influence. Colonialism significantly impacted the Edda judicial system in different ways both negatively and positively.

Negative Impacts:

1. Disruption of traditional institutions: Colonialism weakened the indigenous systems and replaced them with structures that aligned with colonialism. Traditional assemblies which were the bedrock of the traditional judicial system were sidelined and in some cases ignored.
2. Imposition of foreign legal systems (British common law): the local laws and autonomy was suppressed, reducing the ability to resolve disputes autonomously.
3. Marginalization and communal justice: The pre-colonial judicial system of Edda emphasised on restorative justice, while colonial system encouraged punishment measures which conflicted with the restorative system in Edda.
4. Loss of autonomy and cultural identity: Colonialism contributed to the loss of traditional autonomy and cultural identity. The pre-colonial judicial system of Edda was more of a cultural expression which was eroded with colonialism
5. Cultural erosion and identity loss; the introduction of Christianity led to suppression of pagan practices and religion. Trials by oath taking was seen as an abomination to the Christian folks.

Positive Impacts:

1. Modernization of judicial processes: It gave access to broader framework by creating opportunities to modernise outdated practices while trying to maintain elements of traditional system.
2. Introduction of new legal concepts: Colonialism introduced new legal concepts such as the rule of law and due process. It also prohibited some forms of traditional forms of punishment and introducing new ones through colonial legal system.
3. Standardization dispute resolution: It introduced ways of resolving disputes between communities which brought about reduction in intergroup disputes.
4. Economic development: The colonial legal system supported economic development through the establishment of poverty laws and trade regulation which encouraged commerce among communities.

Colonialism significantly affected Edda justice in various ways. It suppressed traditional authority structures and undermined customary law and practices and imposed of foreign legal systems. Edda people lost control over justice administration because colonial authorities made decisions on behalf of Edda community through

courts of law. Colonialism eroded community's ability to resolve disputes internally, suppressed traditional practices and customs, promoted Western values and norms and undermined most Edda cultural identity. Colonialism brought changes to traditional dispute resolution, replaced communal dispute resolution with individualistic approach and introduced new punishments imprisonment which was unfamiliar to Edda culture.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the Pre-colonial judicial system in Edda land from 1800 to 1857 was a unique system that reflected the cultural values and beliefs of Edda people. It was ingrained in community value, conflict resolution, peace and harmony. It was more of an expression of values, norms and community based governance that emphasized restorative justice. Its legacy continues to shape the modern legal system in Edda and serves as a reminder of the rich history and traditions of the community. However, with the arrival of British colonial power in the 19th century, the pre-colonial judicial system in Edda went through significant changes. The British introduced a new system that incorporated elements of their own legal system, significantly altering the traditional practices and beliefs of the Edda people. The traditional Edda justice emphasized restorative justice, community involvement, and cultural values. Justice was communal, frequently relying on consensus, and aimed at restoring relationships than harsh punishments. This led to a gradual decline of the pre-colonial judicial system, as it was replaced by the British legal system. The role of the elders and traditional leaders diminished, and the customary laws were gradually replaced by the British laws.

However, the pre-colonial judicial system in Edda also faced some challenges and limitations such as bias and power imbalance which sometimes led to inconsistencies in justice delivery. But it was a vital institution that settled disputes in manners that was suitable for the people. Though the system was not perfect because it relied so much on oral tradition, but it served its purpose as a tool to holistic justice that brought peace and harmony in Edda.

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